

The Association between gender and mental health among working professionals in non-governmental organisations, Bangalore

B. Preethi Meena¹, Dr. Suphala² & Adele Santamaria³

¹Project Coordinator- Employability skills, Diya Foundation, Bangalore, India

OrcidID: 0000-0001-7665-7357; Email: preethimeena204@gmail.com

²Research Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

OrcidID: 0000-0002-5747-4982; Email: suphalakotian.cssh@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

³BA in psychology, St. Joseph's College (Autonomous), Bangalore, India

OrcidID: 0000-0002-8676-3775; Email: adelesantamaria1994@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) are institutions, recognized by governments as non-profit or welfare oriented, which play an important role on diverse issues pertaining to human and social advancement. NGos have and are continuing to play a key role in betterment of the society and contribute to overall development of the country. To build a strong organisation one of the main pillars is the human resource. Although working professionals contribute to mental health services of large communities, there is comparatively little research done to understand the mental health of working professionals in the NGo sector. Men and women experience different kinds of mental health problems [1]. Thus, in this study the researcher aims to describe the association between gender (male and female) and mental health among working professionals in the NGo sector.*

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: *The researcher has relied on both, primary and secondary data sources. Online survey has been conducted. This is a pilot study to understand the research gap and thus a sample size of 30 participants were selected through stratified sampling random technique lottery method.*

Results: *The study shows the acceptability of the research hypothesis - there is a statistically significant association between gender and mental health.*

Originality/ Value: *The researcher adopted the DASS21 scale by Authors Henry JD, Crawford JR to measure the depression, anxiety and stress of the population. The researcher investigates the coping strategies and solutions contributing to the mental health of the population. With this background, the paper also underlines the implications of future research and practice.*

Paper type: *Descriptive research*

Keywords: Gender, Mental health, Depression, Stress, Anxiety, NGo, Disability professionals

1. INTRODUCTION:

At every stage of an individual mental health plays an important role. Mental health comprises social well being, emotional well being and psychological well being. Mental health helps to determine how an individual thinks, feels, acts in different situations, makes choices, handles stress etc. When people are mentally healthy, they make better decisions, maintain good health and stay positive. This enables them to build strong relationships, handle tough situations and enjoy their life. Through good mental health the individual realizes their abilities, helps them to cope up with normal stresses and can contribute better at the workplace and in the community. The World Health Organization states that gender is a critical determinant of mental health. Studies on mental health and gender shows that socially constructed differences among men and women in taking up responsibilities, those who are in status and power contribute to differences in nature of mental health problems. In a developing country like India, mental health is often perceived with stigma associated with those facing mental illness [2]. Non-Governmental

Organizations (NGOs) are institutions, recognized by governments as non-profit or welfare oriented, which play an important role on diverse issues pertaining to human and social advancement. NGOs continue to play a key role in betterment of the society and contribute to overall development of the country. For an organisation to work for the betterment of the community, it is important to balance the mental health of professionals working towards the vision.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

India being the second most populated country and world's largest industrial nations, continues to face a health crisis [3]. There are still many people who do not receive required interventions and medical treatment. This study focuses on understanding the association between gender and mental health. There are many studies conducted to understand the factors that contribute to mental health. To support this, a study stated that the power and control men and women have on their socioeconomic factors and their mental well being [4] Mental Health Survey Initiative to determine the variation in time-space among female gender as measured by added patterns of female education, employment, marital timing, and use of birth control [5]. Mental health is often perceived with social stigma because of which many people facing mental challenges still do not open up about it. Prejudice toward people with mental illnesses were commonplace among the mental health professionals and may contribute to an inclination among therapists [6]. In psychiatry there are studies that states that sex and gender differences can factor mental disorders. Differences exist regarding prevalence, symptomatology, risk factors and influencing factors among different gender roles [7]. Promoting mental health practices along with developing professionals must go hand in hand as it is an interlinked learning process. Community workers, Youth workers, Service providers play a vital part in promoting and enhancing the mental health literacy of people in the community and thus must be an integral part in professional development [8]. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have played a significant role in the last few decades in not only helping bridge this gap, but also by creating low-cost replicable models of care [9]. Non government organizations being active in a wide array of areas to empower and upskill many beneficiaries.

2. OBJECTIVES:

The Aim of this study is to understand the association between gender and mental health of working professionals in Non government organisations in Bangalore. Following are the objectives of this study

1. To measure the mental health of working professionals in Non Governmental Organisations.
2. To analyse the coping strategies of participants.
3. To suggest suitable measures and best practices to ensure a good mental health of the professionals working in Non government organisations.

4. METHODOLOGY:

The present study was conducted in the Silicon Valley of India, Bengaluru, Karnataka also known as a hub of most of the tech companies around the world. It is also known as the Garden city with its year bound blossoms and greenery. Although non government organisations are striving together with the government to promote mental health and well being, there is significantly lesser importance given to the professionals working for the cause. To understand the present status of mental health of these professionals has encouraged the researcher to conduct this study. The present study uses convergent parallel dynamic design that includes both qualitative and quantitative elements in the same phase of research method which is created by gathering, analyzing, and presenting collected information. This research design consists of a detailed procedure of information that is required to structure the further research. It facilitates smooth functioning of the research process as it has a significant impact on reliability of the outcome of the research. The study obtains quantitative data of 30 individuals who are employed in Non government Organisations using an online survey. The researcher included only those who work in organisations for Person with Intellectual disability and who are currently employed. The researcher excluded those who were either moved to different cities or sectors. The survey contains details of socio- demographic details of the participants and to measure the mental health the researcher used The Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale - 21 Items (DASS-21) which is a set of three self-report scales designed to measure the emotional states of depression, anxiety and stress. It was developed by Lovibond et al in 1983. The researcher obtained Stratified Simple Random sampling technique using the lottery method to study the 30 respondents who obtain a common characteristic such as those who are associated with working in Non-Government organisations towards empowerment or training Persons with Intellectual Disability for quantitative data who were informed about the aim and need for the study well in advance

and their consent has been recorded. Secondary data was also considered for the study by the researcher thus adding to the in depth understanding of the objective of the study. The researcher used descriptive research design. The collected data was focused on a thematic analysis and organizing sequentially that includes collection of data, generating the information, reviewing the information and lastly documenting the findings. In this present study the researcher has used MS Excel to upload the raw data. In order to analyze the uploaded data, the researcher has used PSPP statistical software.

5.ASSOCIATIONBETWEENGENDERANDMENTALHEALTH:

Data analysis and interpretation is the process of systematically applying logical methods to describe and evaluate data. It helps to build credibility of the research by giving a theoretical base. It deals with analyzing the data collected and interpretation of the information in detail by using tables, graphs and pie charts. Following are the brief analysis and interpretation of variables used for the study. To understand the nature of the respondent, the researcher collected socio demographic data of the participants. Following are the Socio demographic details of the participants-

Graph 01 - Graphical representation of participant's age (30 participants)

Graph - 2: Graphical representation of participant's Gender

(15 females and 15 males)

Graph 3: Graphical Representation of Participant's Work Experience

*Following shows the association between gender and mental health in 3 parameters
Table 01 - Gender vs stress level*

		Below average level	Above average level	Total
Gender	Male	5(31.3%)	10(71.4%)	15
	Female	11(68.8%)	4 (28.6%)	15
Total		16	14	30
	Value	df	Exact sign. (2 tailored)	
Chi square	4.82	1	0.037	

The result in table 01 indicates the fact that a higher percentage of male (71.4 percent) have an above average level of stress compared to females(28.6 percent). Moreover the results show a statistically significant association between gender and stress with moderate level of accuracy.

Table 02 - Gender vs Anxiety

		Below average level	Above average level	Total
Gender	Male	4 (26.7%)	11 (73.3%)	15
	Female	11 (73.3%)	4 (26.7%)	15
Total		15	15	30
	Value	df	Exact sign. (2 tailored)	
Chi square	6.53	1	.015	

The result in table 02 indicates the fact that a higher percentage of females (73.3 percent) have below average level of anxiety compared to male(26.7 percent). Moreover the results show a statistically significant association between gender and anxiety with moderate level of accuracy.

Table 03- Gender vs Depression

		Below average level	Above average level	Total
Gender	Male	5 (29.4%)	10 (76.9%)	15
	Female	12 (70.6%)	3 (23.1%)	15
Total		17	13	30
	Value	df	Exact sign. (2 tailored)	

Chi square	6.55	1	.014
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The result in table 03 indicate the fact that among females , a greater percentage of respondents (70.6 percent) have below average levels of depression. Moreover the results show a statistically significant association between gender and depression with moderate level of accuracy.

6. SUGGESTIONS and RECOMMENDATIONS:

The participants use varied mechanisms and practices to vent out their stress , anxiety or feelings. The researcher used open ended questions to understand their coping strategies. It was found that some prefer going to bed early and ensure they get about 7 to 8 hours to rest. Whereas others spend quality time with their families and peers regularly. The coping strategies could vary from person to person as their social -environment varies. Emotional and mental stability and well being is a vital part of everybody's lives and it impacts one's thoughts, actions and behaviour. To develop gender specific services it is essential to evaluate their profession and their coping strategies [10]. With this background the researcher suggests the following measures:

1. NGOs adopt Capacity Building and Well Being Training to practice Balanced Mental Health for their employees on a regular basis.
2. Institution to appoint an Organizational Psychologist and assess the mental health of employees and suggest appropriate interventions.
3. Ensure the organisation provides a suitable space for their employees to share their feelings and thoughts in order to address concerns if any.

7. CONCLUSION:

Men and women experience different kinds of mental health problems. Mental and physical health are equally important components of overall health. For example, depression increases the risk for many types of physical health problems[11]. Thus, this study has proved the rejection of the Null hypothesis - There is no association between gender and mental health - and the acceptance of the Research hypothesis - There is an association between gender and mental health. The reasons for above average mental health (depression , stress and anxiety) could vary from person to person and the social environment that they are a part of . When adults focus on producing quality work it is important for them to understand the balance between work and life resulting in good mental health.

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